

Haematological Parameters in Chronic Kidney Disease

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ABSTRACT

Chronic Kidney disease is a condition where gradual decline of renal function can happen with time, leading to end-stage renal disease. The early detection becomes relevant to avoid the progression and this study aimed to analyse the haematological parameters in CKD stages 3, 4 and 5 with a comparative evaluation of those that do not require hemodialysis and those managed by hemodialysis.

A 2ml EDTA blood sample of the patient was analyzed in an automated 6-part analyzer with peripheral smear prepared. eGFR was calculated with CKD-EPI formula with patients categorized into stages 3,4 and 5, with 26 patients in each. A comparison analysis of haematological parameters was done between stages.

Mean age remained around 60 with most cases having normocytic normochromic anemia Total count increased with neutrophilia with other differential counts within normal range. There is decrease in RBC count and hematocrit with increase in immature granulocytes. Mean corpuscular volume, Mean corpuscular hemoglobin and hemoglobin concentration with retic and Immature reticulocyte fraction remained in normal range with mean reticulocyte hemoglobin equivalent decreased. Mean platelet count remained within normal level with increase in Mean platelet volume and mean Platelet distribution width with progression of stages. As the duration of dialysis increased, total count decreased. Hemoglobin, RBC count with hematocrit decreased. Red cell indices increased and Platelet count decreased with increase in Mean platelet volume.

Analysing these differences at the earliest will help in better management of CKD and helps to impede the progression from 3 to 5 stages.

KEYWORDS: Chronic kidney Disease, Haematological parameters, hemodialysis, stage 3,4,5, anemia

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I. INTRODUCTION

The prevalence of CKD and its high cost of treatment make it a global public health issue. With an international incidence of 8–16%, CKD is the 17th most common cause of disability and the 12th most cause of mortality. According to the National Kidney Foundation of India, 2 lakh people have fatal renal failure each year due to renal disease, which is listed third among diseases that are life-threatening after cancer.¹

According to the CKD registry of India's database, 150–200 people in India have the end-stage renal disease (ESRD) on an annual basis, with diabetes mellitus serving as a major contributing factor. Based on the expected GFR, CKD is

divided into five stages. Approximately 6% of adults have CKD stages 1 and 2, while 4.5% have stages 3 and 4.

CKD stages 3 and 4 are usually managed without dialysis, whereas stage 5 is managed by dialysis. CKD influences the haematological parameters. Hemodialysis can further modify these effects. The biggest issue facing public health is the precise identification of CKD; without frequent surveillance of renal function, most patients with CKD had advanced stages when they were discovered.

Comparative analysis of haematological parameters between CKD stages 3 and 4, which do not require hemodialysis, and CKD stage 5, which requires hemodialysis, is done.

Haematological Parameters in Chronic Kidney Disease

Knowledge of these subtle differences can pave the way for better clinical management.

II. METHODS

A Prospective Analytical study over 2 years (Dec 2020 to April 2022) was done in the Department of Pathology, JSS Medical College and Hospital, Mysore. All consecutive cases of CKD in stages 3,4 &5 were included. Patients with CKD who have undergone kidney transplantation and presenting with acute renal failure were excluded from the study.

In a study of 78 cases,26 cases of CKD stages 3,4 and 5 were taken. The sample size is calculated based on mean Hb levels among patients with CKD to be 7.76 ± 2.50 with the allowable error of 0.2 with $\alpha = 5\%$ and 95% and Confidence level to be 78, divided equally among 3 stages-stage 3,4 and 5.

Clinical details and Demographic data of the CKD patients were collected, eGFR was calculated using the CKD-EPI formula, and patients were categorized into stages 3,4 and 5. 2ml EDTA blood sample of each patient was analyzed in an automated 6- part haematology analyzer of Mindray company (model: BC -6200), and a peripheral smear was prepared after staining with Leishman.

Data of all haematology parameters, such as Hb, TC, DC, Immature granulocytes, RBC count, Hematocrit, MCV, MCH, MCHC, Reticulocyte count, IRF, RHE, platelet count, MPV, PDW, IPF were entered in the excel sheet., and a comparison was done between CKD patients' stages 3 and 4, which are managed without dialysis and stage 5, managed with dialysis.

III. STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

Data collected was entered in MS Excel 2010 and analyzed using the SPSS version. Descriptive statistical measures like percentage, mean and standard deviation were applied, and inferential statistical tests like Anova were applied to find the difference in haematological parameters across stages. Differences were interpreted as statistically significant at p-value < 0.05 .

Informed consents were obtained from the patients or bystanders after describing the details of the study by means of printed informed consent form and Ethical committee clearance was obtained before beginning the study.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Haematological parameters of 78 cases of patients of CKD were analyzed in this study after categorizing these 78 cases with 26 cases each in stages 3,4, and 5. The ages of the cases collected were from 31-75 years, considering all stages, with a median age of 50 years for stage 3,60 years for stage 4 and 56 years for stage 5. (Figure 1). According to studies by George et al.,60 % of the cases were aged > 61 years, Bhattacharjee et al., 3 the predominant age group was

51 to 60 and Dewan et al., 4 most cases in 70-80 years and Cindy George et al. 5 with a median age of 50.

Figure 1. Age distribution of cases of Stages 3,4, 5 of CKD.

In the present study,22 were females,56 were males, with a predominance of males in all stages, with 84.6% males in stage 3,61.5% in stage 4 and 69.2% in stage 5. George et al 2 Bhattacharjee et al. 3 and Dewan et al. 4 all had male predominance in their studies. (Figure 2)

Figure 2. Gender distribution of cases of Stages 3,4, 5 of CKD

In stage 3,17 out of 26 cases had anaemia with mean Hb - 11.8 gm/dl. In stage 4,25 cases had anaemia with mean Hb 9.5 gm/dl, and 25 cases had anaemia in stage 5. Considering all the stages, most CKD patients had a median Hb of 8.7 - 11.6 gm/dl. So haemoglobin decreased as the stages progressed from stage 3 to 5 due to insufficiency of the production of erythropoietin The previous studies by George et al 2 ,Bhattacharjee et al. 3 and Dewan et al. 4 also had similar results with lower Hb. (Table 1)

Total WBC count increased with neutrophilia predominant.54% of all cases of CKD showed WBC count within normal limits, and 41 % showed an increase in WBC count. Neutrophils % ranged from 70-83 % considering all stages. It is analogous to the previous studies of Dewan et al.4 Bhattacharjee et al. 3 & George et al.2 This may be due to the chronic inflammatory state of CKD, where interleukins like IL-6 are released into the blood (Table 1)

In stage 3 CKD, the mean lymphocyte was 18%. In stage 4, 14.1% and stage 5, 14.8 %, respectively. Mean lymphocyte % remained within normal limits. According to the study by Cindy George et al. 5 and Afshan Zeeshan et al. 6 decreased

Haematological Parameters in Chronic Kidney Disease

lymphocyte count was associated with reduced eGFR. In those studies, the Neutrophil/Lymphocyte ratio was proposed as a prognostic indicator with this ratio inversely related to eGFR.

2 out of 26 cases showed Eosinophilia in stage 3, 3 cases each of stage 4 and stage 5 CKD showed Eosinophilia in the present study. The mean eosinophil percentage remained within normal limits which conformed with the study by Cindy George et al., 5 which showed the median eosinophil count to be 0.2. (Table 1)

Mean monocyte % remained within normal limits with 4.2% for Stage 3, 4.4% for stage 4 and 4% for stage 5. This is following study by Cindy George et al.5, where monocytes lie in the interquartile range of 0.4-0.6%. However, this is against the study by Afshan Zeeshan et al. 6, where monocyte counts decreased.

In the study by Tandi et al.5, the basophil ranged between (0-0.1%) in various stages of CKD, indicating no variation in the same with the progression of CKD. The minimum basophil count in stage 3 was 0.1%, maximum was 2%. Maximum basophil count was 1% each in stage 4 and stage 5. (Table 1)

Immature granulocytes are now an emerging biomarker of inflammation in CKD. In the current study, the maximum value of immature granulocytes in % increased as the stage progressed with positive correlation with increase in neutrophil %. This may be because of the increased release of inflammatory cytokines like IL-1 and TNF- α in stage 5. This follows the study by Cetin et al. 4 where they compared immature granulocytes% with the inflammation in the pre-dialysis stages of CKD. (Table 1)

The mean RBC Count was within the normal limit in almost all stages, with the count progressively decreasing with the stage. This agrees with the previous study by Tandi et al.5 and Afshan Zeeshan et al.6, where RBC count decreased with the decrease in haemoglobin. Disordered iron homeostasis, insufficient erythropoietin production along with shortened RBC survival decreased RBC count. (Table 1)

Analogous to the study by Afshan Zeeshan Wasti et al. 6 where PCV were lowered in CKD patients as compared to the controls, due to increased destruction of red blood cells with decreased erythropoietin production in stage 5 CKD, In this study also, mean hematocrit levels decreased.

The mean MCV value was around 85-89 fL in all stages of CKD with a predominant population of normocytic RBCs. (Table 1). Mean MCH was found to be within the normal reference range in all the stages of CKD similar to the results observed in studies by Talwar et al. and Alghythan et al. 7 MCHC, the measure of Hb concentration, was also within the normal reference range in all the stages of CKD, which is similar to the study by Cindy George et al.5

In this study, the mean retic % was 2.1, 2.2 and 2.3 in stages 3, 4 and 5, respectively. This finding does not agree with the study by Abdulrahman Y et al.8, who reported a high retic

count in CKD patients due to hematologic growth factors stimulating erythropoiesis. (Table 1)

RHE (Reticulocyte Hb equivalent) is direct measurement of iron level of reticulocytes and determine the forward scatter of fluorescence labelled reticulocytes and is an early and sensitive indicator of iron deficiency anemia. Mean RHE was found to be around 27 which is decreased in all the stages with lowest value in stage 5 CKD. This may be due to functional iron deficient erythropoiesis which accords with the study by Husni et al 9 (Table 1)

IRF measures the fraction that stains more for RNA and assesses the maturity of circulating reticulocytes..IRF was within the reference range, in all the stages and it is positively correlated with iron deficiency anaemia.

Mean platelet count remained within the normal level in all the 3 stages of CKD, i.e., platelet count was adequate in 65% of stage 3, 77% of stage 4 and 73.2 % of stage 5. 26.9% of stage 3 and 23% each of stage 4 and stage 5 showed a decrease in number. This decrease in platelet count may be because of decreased erythropoietin levels in stage 5, as there is a homology between erythropoietin and thrombopoietin. This agrees with the study by Cindy George et al. 5 and Afshan et al.6, as thrombocytopenia was seen in 56% of cases.

MPV measures the average size of platelets found in the blood. The mean MPV of CKD patients was within the normal reference range of 8.9-11.8 fL with 10.1 fL mean MPV considering all three stages of MPV. As MPV did not make much difference in various stages, it could not be used to compare various stages. The maximum value of MPV increased in stage 4 and stage 5 CKD when compared with stage 3. (Table 1) as MPV is an important biomarker of inflammation and a crucial prognostic indicator of cardiovascular diseases. Equating with the study by Ju et al., where higher MPV was seen in CKD, which is more progressive than in early-stage CKD. 10 (Table 1) indicating there is increased incidence of other comorbidities like Diabetes mellitus, Hypertension and risk factors like smoking . hypercholesterolemia with progression in the chronicity of inflammatory state in stage 4 and stage 5 CKD. The size similarity of the platelets is measured by platelet distribution width. High PDW indicates a wide range in size and is a crucial gauge of platelet activity with a greater value indicating higher mortality and cardiovascular morbidity. (Table 1). PDW was towards the higher limit of the normal range in stage 5, and PDW mean value increased with the progression of the stage. This is like the study of Mahmoud Mousa et al 11, where PDW increased in patients undergoing hemodialysis compared to the control group. The mean IPF value was within the normal range in all stages of CKD. (Table 1)

The stages of CKD are divided into 5 based on creatinine and eGFR. The mean value of creatinine increased from 1.8 mg/dl in stage 3 to 6.8 mg/dl in stage 5. i.e., As the stage progressed from 3 to 5, creatinine value increased with

Haematological Parameters in Chronic Kidney Disease

decreased creatinine clearance by the kidney at stage 5, where there is a maximum loss of kidney function. This follows the study by Dara Khorshid¹².

The mean value of eGFR decreased from eGFR of 40.7 in stage 3 to 8.7 in stage 5, due to increased loss of nephrons in stage 5 compared to stage 3. (Table 1)

Normocytic normochromic anemia is the most common anemia in CKD with appearance of increased morphological alterations in the RBC in stage 5 with the presence of Burr cells, microcytes (Figure 3). Anisocytosis was found to be more in stage 4 CKD than in stage 3 CKD. (Table 1) These changes follow studies by Bhattacharjee et al.³, where 61% had normocytic anaemia. Toxic granules were seen in 3.8% of each of stages 4 and stage 5. Giant platelets were seen in 11.5% of patients with stage 4 CKD. (Figure 4)

Figure 4. Toxic granules with Giant platelets(Leishman staining,100x)

As the duration of dialysis increased, the total WBC count decreased. This is against the studies by Dara Khorshid et al.¹², where the WBC count was increased in patients with renal failure after the hemodialysis process. Neutrophils, eosinophils increased with lymphocytes and monocytes decreased with the duration of dialysis. Due to inflammation-induced leukocytosis associated with dialysis, there is positive correlation of immature granulocytes with the dialysis duration. (Table 2)

With the duration of dialysis, Hemoglobin and RBC count decreased. Hematocrit also decreased. MCV, MCH, MCHC increased with the duration of dialysis. This was against study by Dara Khorshid et al ¹² where hemoglobin concentration increased in patient in comparison before hemodialysis. PCV also increased after hemodialysis.

Retic count is usually seen increased with erythropoietin treatment. But here, as duration of dialysis increased, retic count decreased which may be due to long history of disease, severity, and decreased improvement with the treatment even though it is statistically not significant. (Table 2). IRF, RHE increased with dialysis.

RHE is used as a reliable tool to diagnose iron deficiency and predicts response to iron in hemodialysis patients. In iron deficiency anemia, there is erythropoietin stress and bone marrow respond to this by increased activity and increased IRF. This is comparable with the study by Patricia et al. ¹³

As the duration of dialysis increased, platelet decreased. MPV, IPF and PDW increased. (Table 2) Increased platelet consumption with decreased platelet count and release of immature platelet from bone marrow as a compensatory mechanism due to complement activation induced by interaction of blood and dialyser membrane **results in** increased IPF. This is in conformity with the study by Taha Bat et al.¹⁴

In line with the study by Wang et al ¹⁶ and Mahmoud Mousa et al ¹⁵, PDW increased in patients who undergo hemodialysis when compared to the control group because of increased chronicity of inflammatory state and increased activation and aggregation of platelets due to exposure to dialysis membranes.

Table 1: Comparison of Hematological parameters in different stages of CKD.

Parameters	Stage 3 Mean (SD)	Stage 4 Mean (SD)	Stage 5 Mean (SD)	p-value
Total Hemoglobin (gm/dl)	11.8(3.3)	9.5(1.5)	8.8(1.5)	0.0002*
Total WBC count (cells/cu.m m)	10692.9(5993.3)	7930.5(5962.0)	10309.6(5304)	0.22
Neutrophil(%)	75.2(10.7)	78.0(11.2)	76.2(10.9)	0.71
Lymphocyte(%)	18.0(8.8)	14.1(7.6)	14.8(7.3)	0.23
Eosinophils (%)	2.3(2.8)	3.0(3.4)	4.6(5.7)	0.27
Monocyte(%)	4.2(1.4)	4.4(1.9)	4.0(1.4)	0.73
Basophils(%)	0.4(0.4)	0.4(0.3)	0.4(0.2)	0.27
Immature Granulocytes (%)	1.3(1.1)	1.5(4.3)	2.0(6.9)	0.00
RBC(10 ⁶ /uL)	4(1.2)	3.3(0.6)	3.1(0.6)	0.001
Hematocrit(%)	35.9(9.4)	29.1(5.3)	26.7(4.6)	0.0002
Mean Capsular Volume(fl)	88.2(6.9)	88(6.5)	85.5(5.1)	0.27
Mean Capsular Haemoglobin(pg)	29.2(2.9)	28.6(2.0)	28.4(1.6)	0.14
Mean	33(1.8)	32.6(1.8)	33.3(1.3)	0.51

Haematological Parameters in Chronic Kidney Disease

Corpuscular haemoglobin Concentration (g/dl))	
Retic(%)	2.1(1.5)	2.2(0.8)	2.3(1.7)	0.8
Immature reticulocyte fraction (%)	9.5(6.2)	10.4(5)	9.9(8.2)	0.62
Reticulocyte hemoglobin equivalent (pg)	27.1(3.6)	27(4.5)	26.4(2.5)	0.69
Platelet count	2.6(1.6)	2.2(0.9)	2.3(1.1)	0.76
Mean platelet volume(fl)	10.1(1.2)	10.1(1.3)	10.2(1.3)	0.93
Immature platelet fraction(%)	2.2(1.6)	4.5(4.8)	2.2(2.2)	0.16
Platelet distribution width (fl)	14.5(3)	13.9(3)	15.6(1.8)	0.26
Creatinine	1.8(0.3)	2.9(0.5)	6.8(2.5)	0.00
eGFR	40.7(8.8)	21.3(4.3)	8.7(3.3)	0.00
*Krusal-Walis test (data expressed in median and IQR) eGFR -Estimated glomerular filtration rate				

Table 2: Statistical significance of hematological parameters with duration of dialysis in CKD stage 5.

HEMATOLOGICAL PARAMETERS	PEARSON CORRELATION	SIGNIFICANCE
HEMOGLOBIN (gm/dl)	-.357	.080
TOTAL WBC COUNT (cells/cu.mm)	-.030	.888
NEUTROPHIL (%)	.196	..349
LYMPHOCYTE (%)	-.207	.320
EOSINOPHIL%	.019	.928
MONOCYTE (%)	-.497*	.011
BASOPHIL (%)	-.290	.160
IMMATURE GRANULOCYTES (%)	.037	.860

RBC (10 ⁶ /uL)	-.390	.054
HCT (%)	-.368	.070
MCV (fl)	.208	.318
MCH (pg)	.227	.276
MCHC(g/dl)	.015	.945
RETIC (%)	-.058	.796
IRF(%)	.037	.871
RHE(pg)	.201	.369
PLATELET	-.077	.715
MPV (fl)	.348	.089
IPF(%)	.523*	.013
PDW (fl)	.077	.714

CONCLUSIONS

Abnormal haematological parameters were shown in stage 3, stage 4 and stage 5 cases of CKD patients. Most patients of stages 3,4, and 5 were within the age group of 50-60 years, with male predominance.

Normocytic normochromic anaemia was the predominant peripheral smear blood picture. Burr cells and fragmented RBCs become most common in stage 5 CKD. The mean RBC Count was within the normal limit in almost all stages, with the count progressively decreasing with the stage. Hematocrit decreased, total count increased with Neutrophilic leukocytosis with associated increased immature granulocytes.

Platelet count remained within the normal reference range. The new haematological parameters RHE, RDW, IRF, MPV, and IPF can be used to monitor CKD's chronicity, inflammatory state, and progression. As the stage progressed from 3 to 5, creatinine value increased, and eGFR decreased. These can be used as an indicator to assess kidney function. There is difference in hematological parameters in patients before dialysis and after dialysis and with the progression of dialysis.

As the duration of dialysis increased, total count decreased. Hemoglobin and RBC count along with hematocrit decreased. MCV, MCH, MCHC increased with duration of dialysis. Platelet decreased, MPV, IPF and PDW increased.

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REFERENCES

1. BEHERA BP. Hematological profile in patients of chronic kidney disease with its severity in a tertiary care hospital, north odisha. Asian J Pharm Clin Res. 2020;13(8):1-6.

Haematological Parameters in Chronic Kidney Disease

- II. George S, Pullockara J, Sailesh K, J K M. A study to assess changes in hematological profile in chronic kidney disease. *The Pharma Innovation*. 2015;4(6):1-3.
- III. Bhattacharjee K, Das D, Rabha P, Kalwar A, Kar G, Bhattacharjee P. A study on haematological profile in patients of chronic renal failure with special reference to serum iron profile. *Journal of Evidence Based Medicine and Healthcare*. 2015;2(46):8212-8219.
- IV. Dewan P, Patil N, Bharti M. Hematological Profile In Cases Of Chronic Renal Diseases. *IOSR Journal of Dental and Medical Sciences*. 2017;16(04):01-03.
- V. George C, Matsha T, Erasmus R, Kengne A. Haematological profile of chronic kidney disease in a mixed-ancestry South African population: a cross-sectional study. *BMJ Open*. 2018;8(11):1-9.
- VI. Afshar R, Sanavi S, Salimi J, Ahmadzadeh M. Hematological profile of chronic kidney disease (CKD) patients in Iran, in pre-dialysis stages and after initiation of hemodialysis. *Saudi Journal of Kidney Diseases and Transplantation*. 2010 Mar 1;21(2):368.
- VII. Talwar VK, Gupta HL, Narayan S. Clinico haematological profile in chronic renal failure. *J Assoc Physicians India* 2002;50:228- 33.
- VIII. Islam MN, Ferdous A, Zahid AZ, Alam M, Islam MN. Haematological profile of patients with chronic kidney disease in Northern Bangladesh. *Dinajpur Med Col J*. 2015 Jan;8(1):1-7.
- IX. Hasibuan H, Nasution S, Tarigan R. Correlation of reticulocyte hemoglobin equivalent (ret-HE) levels and iron deficiency anemia in CKD patients treating regular hemodialysis. *International Journal of Research and Review*. 2021;8(11):10–6.
- X. Ju HY, Kim JK, Hur SM, Woo SA, Park KA, Park MY, Choi SJ, Hwang SD. Could mean platelet volume be a promising biomarker of progression of chronic kidney disease?. *Platelets*. 2015 Feb 17;26(2):143-7.
- XI. Lokesh S, Green SR, Mathew TK, Hemachandar R, Kumar A, Tiwari SR, Lakshmi A, Ezhumalai G. A comparative study of platelet parameters in end stage renal disease patients undergoing haemodialysis and healthy individuals. *Int J Adv Med*. 2016 Aug;3(3):559-63.
- XII. Mohammad DK. Effect of Hemodialysis and peritoneal dialysis on some hematological and biochemical parameters in renal failure. *Zanco Journal of Medical Sciences (Zanco J Med Sci)*. 2009;13(2):79-85.
- XIII. Toki Y, Ikuta K, Kawahara Y, Niizeki N, Kon M, Enomoto M, Tada Y, Hatayama M, Yamamoto M, Ito S, Shindo M. Reticulocyte hemoglobin equivalent as a potential marker for diagnosis of iron deficiency. *International journal of hematology*. 2017 Jul;106(1):116-25.
- XIV. Bat T, Bat BE, El-Moghraby A, Patel S, Feng X, Dunbar CE, Sarac E. Thrombopoietic status of patients on haemodialysis. *British journal of haematology*. 2016 Mar;172(6):954-7.
- XV. Aziz AF, Saad AT, Bazeed MM, Allam MA, Bakeer MS. A comparative study of platelet parameters in chronic kidney disease, end stage renal disease patients undergoing hemodialysis and healthy individuals. *The Egyptian Journal of Hospital Medicine*. 2018 Apr 1;71(6):3429-33.
- XVI. Tunca O, Kazan S, Kazan ED. Can mean platelet volume predicts renal outcome in acute on chronic kidney disease? *Therapeutic Apheresis and Dialysis*. 2022 Sep 27:1-8.